

ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS THROUGH INTERNET WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The Internet has become a major source of the information consumptions, and to some extent, has replaced old media such as the radio, television and the newspapers. The main advantages of the internet include its mass availability and its almost instant access to current information. The Internet today is a widespread information infrastructure, the initial prototype of what is often called the national information infrastructure. Its history is complex and involves many aspects technological, organizational, and community. And its influence reaches not only to the technical fields of computer communications but throughout society as we move toward increasing use of online tools to accomplish electronic commerce and community operations.

Key Words: Internet, Advertising, Viewers & Awareness

Introduction:

The word advertising is derived from the Latin word viz, "advertero" "ad" meaning towards and "verto" meaning towards and "verto" meaning. "I turn" literally specific thing". Advertising is a means of communication with the users if a product or service. Advertisements are message paid for by those who send them and are intended to inform or influence people who receive them, as defined by the Advertising Association of the UK. It then includes interest, develops a desire and finally motivates consumers to take an action. Organizations have been continuously increasing their advertisement budgets to attract more customers. Manufactures use advertising to reach the individual customers for attaining the sales of a product, brand or a service. They also use advertising to reach resellers such a wholesalers and retailers to purchase their products and services and resell them to their respective customers. Advertisement is the quickest least expensive and most effective media for communicating with people. It helps to find quickly what they want to buy, where to buy, how to buy and buy them easily. It also educates people to make effectiveness use of the product. Advertisement is a dynamic activity and is constantly changing in response to changes in the world of business. It is promotional activity for marketing a commodity. It is only through proper advertising a new product can be introduced in the market. The effectiveness of adverting depends upon to what extent the advertising message is received and accepted by the target audience. Advertising media plays an important role of providing the effective communication between the marketer and consumer. There are different types of advertising media available to the advertisers like radio, television and now World Wide Web internet too. In developing an advertising programme, one must always start by identifying the market needs and buyer motives and must make five major decisions commonly referred as 5M (mission, money message, media and measurement) of advertising.

Internet:

Internet is the "network of networks" that operators on a set of technical protocols that enables people from around the world to access and exchange information using tools such as the World Wide Web, e-mail, chat rooms, etc. Today, more than 700 million people use the internet daily, mostly so in developed countries. (USA, China, Japan, Germany & Britain) The most popular uses of the internet are searching through data and information, and the purchasing of products and services. In light of these, it is understandable why many companies advertise can quickly benefit from changing advertising scripts, from the possibility of better segmenting their market, and from relatively low costs. Due to internet advertising proliferation, it is important to examine the factors that affect its effectiveness. The internet grew out of the Advanced Research projects agency's Wide area network (then called ARPANET) established by the US department of defense in 1960s for collaboration in military research among business and government laboratories. The Internet contains billions of web pages created by people and companies from around the world, making it a limitless place to locate information and entertainment. The internet also has thousands of services that help make life more convenient. As we have referenced before, the growth of advertising via the Internet is growing dramatically but sporadically. In 1995, \$54.7 million was spent advertising on the internet, and the year 2000 logged in at just over \$8 billion. In 2002, billions went out of the Internet advertisement market and revenues came in at just over \$6 billion. By 2003, a recovery was in process and revenues spiked back to \$7.25 billion, reached about \$250 billion in 2008. Advertising on television, newspaper, bill boards or direct mail is based on large exposure and particularly wide audience. On the other hand is based on relatively few channels that

coalesce to bring forth a maximized target customer. Internet advertising helps to market products services through interactive and colorful catalogs and provides audience with current and available information. Today, there are numerous websites designed to promote sales and to maintain relationship with customers. Internet advertising is the means of promoting a product on the internet using various Internet features. The primary benefit of Internet advertising is that it surpasses all geographical boundaries, which cannot be gained locally. Internet advertising also called online marketing. Internet advertising has gained immense importance and is now crucial platform in brand development, brand promotion and brand management. Advertising is being done through websites, social networking sites to reach out to consumers who are now heavily dependent on technology and above all the internet. As a new advertising channel the Internet and particularly the World Wide Web portion of the Internet, are challenging traditional forms of mass media advertising. The Internet offers an interactive alternative to mass media communication through the use of web pages, discussion groups and email. Internet advertising was perceived to be informative, entertaining, useful, valuable, and important.

Review of Literature:

Thomas P. Novak et.al. (1996) made an attempt to study the response of consumers towards internet advertisements. Their empirical evidence suggested that consumers respond too much of the advertising on the Internet in the same ways as they respond to advertising in traditional media, at least with respond to traditional measures of advertising effectiveness. Internet and other interactive media like television have been more powerful, responsive a customizable than traditional media.

Laurent Flores (2000) conducted a study to experience of how internet advertising works and how it contributes to brand building and the value of different online advertising formats ranging from banner and sponsorship to rich media. He then investigates the current challenges and potentials of internet advertising with a specific emphasis on the promising challenge of mixed media strategies, integrating online advertising and other traditional types of advertising.

Goldsmith and Lafferty (2002) have studied in terms of consumer responses in the form of liking online advertisement, researchers such as have found that a more favorable attitude towards advertisements can lead to higher ability to recall advertisement. In general, research suggests that those consumers who have a positive attitude toward an advertisement are more able to recall than those with a negative attitude made a similar conclusion but the study was based on print advertising performance.

Statement of the Problem:

Media and advertisement both are interrelated and affects each other in many ways. Advertisers are expected to shift and spend millions in internet advertising in the coming years than TV, print advertisement and other traditional advertising media. Internet is one of the significant mediums that own all kinds of features, which implies a great potential and powerful advertising medium in the future the problem is that, volumes of consumers are online every day for their personal work, sometimes fake advertisements are provided to the internet advertisement. It will take long time to delivery of products and not in good quality of product. Internet Advertisement is not convenient for all time. Lack of security and network reliability become the major obstacle to the internet.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To determine the relationship between internet advertising and purchase decision.
- ✓ To know the satisfaction level of the respondents.

Research Methodology:

This research paper focuses on research methodology that was used in the study. It provides a detailed description of the research approach adopted in this study. Research design, sampling design, data collection, data analysis and tools used were presented in the subsequent section.

Research Design:

This study is based on the primary data. The primary data was collected from 80 respondents. However necessary care has been to include respondents from different areas of Coimbatore district.

Sampling Design:

The researcher used convenient sampling method by which 80 samples were selected for the study.

Data Collections:

Primary data was collected from 80 respondents through questionnaire. Each questionnaire consists of 28 questions. It covers all the internet users such as employees, professionals, and so on. The secondary data mainly consists of information collected mainly from various newspaper, magazines and website etc.

Scope of the Study:

The study may benefit marketers, business, government and academicians. This study may be able to inform marketers on the consumer preference of the advertising media and whether using Internet advertising,

would be effective in reaching and increasing awareness of the target audience. Internet advertising is creating an ambient environment and availing resource to internet providing companies and at the same time safeguarding the interest of consumers.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ Since the study has been conducted with 80 respondents that the study may reveal the results based on the sample size.
- ✓ It is only focused on the Internet Advertisement viewers only.
- ✓ Since the study is conducted only in Coimbatore district.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Opinion of the Internet Advertisements:

The table shows that out of 80 respondents, 56% of the respondents are opinion about attractive of internet advertisement, 25% of the respondents are to feel about Exploring of internet advertisement and 19% of the respondents are to feel about the internet advertisement are disturbing. Most of the respondents are opinion about attractive of internet advertisement

Table 1: Products Purchased Through Internet Advertisement

Products	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Electronics	29	43
Books	16	24
Home Appliances	11	16
Cosmetics	7	10
Others	5	7
Total	68	100

Source: Primary Data

The table displays that of 80 respondents 43% of the respondents purchased electronics items through internet advertisements, 25% of the respondents purchased books through internet advertisement, 15% of the respondents purchased home appliances through internet advertisement, 11% of the respondents purchased cosmetic through internet advertisement and 6% of the respondents purchased other category of goods through internet advertisement. Most of the respondents purchased electronic items through internet advertisement.

Table 2: Characteristics of the Internet Advertisement

Characteristics	Total	Mean Score	Rank
Clarity	233	2.91	VI
Simple	237	2.96	V
Informative	228	2.85	VIII
Colorful	230	2.87	VII
Unique	220	2.75	IX
Appearance	244	3.05	IV
Meaningful	233	2.91	VI
Create Awareness	264	3.3	II
Attractive	273	3.41	I
Visibility	247	3.09	III

Source: Primary Data

From the table is inferred that the characteristics of internet advertisement is ‘Attractive’ with the highest mean of 3.41, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Create Awareness’ with the 2nd highest mean of 3.3, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Visibility’ with 3rd highest mean of 3.09, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Appearance’ with 4th highest mean of 3.05, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Simple’ with 5th highest mean of 2.96, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Clarity’ and ‘Meaningful’ with 6th highest mean of 2.91, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Colorful’ with the 7th highest mean of 2.87, followed by internet advertisement is ‘Informative’ with 8th highest mean of 2.85, and followed by internet advertisement is ‘Unique’ with 9th highest mean of 2.75. The characteristic of internet advertisement is ‘Attractive’ with the highest mean of 3.41.

Table 3: Opinion about the Internet Advertisement Respondents

Factors	Total	Mean Score	Rank
Creative	270	3.37	VI
Reasonable Price	259	3.24	VII
Variety	297	3.71	III

Delivery Time	278	3.47	V
Discount	298	3.72	II
Easy to buy	317	3.96	I
Service	289	3.61	IV

Source: Primary Data

From the table is inferred that the opinion about the internet advertisement respondents is ‘Easy to buy’ with the highest mean of 3.96, followed by internet advertisement respondents is ‘Discount’ with the 2nd highest mean of 3.72, followed by internet advertisement respondents is ‘Variety’ with 3rd highest mean of 3.71, followed by internet advertisement respondents is ‘Service’ with 4th highest mean of 3.61, followed by internet advertisement respondents is ‘Delivery Time’ with 5th highest mean of 3.47, followed by internet advertisement respondents is ‘Creative’ with 6th highest mean of 3.37, and followed by internet advertisement respondents of ‘Reasonable Price’ with the 7th highest mean of 3.24. The opinion about the internet advertisement respondents is ‘Easy to buy’ with the highest mean of 3.96.

Table 4: Internet advertisement influencing the Purchase Decision

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Influence	20	25
Influence	44	55
Neutral	12	15
Not Influence	4	5
Total	80	100

Source: Primary Data

The table reveals that out of 80 respondents, 25% of the respondents feels that internet advertisement highly influence purchase decision, 55% of the respondents influence purchase decision, 15% of the respondents feel neutral about the internet advertisement and 5% of the respondents feel internet advertisement not influence the purchase decision. Most of the respondents feel that internet advertisement influence purchase decision.

Table 5: Reason to Purchases through Internet Advertisement

Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Price	16	20
Offers	24	30
Range of products	20	25
Convenience	20	25
Total	80	100

Source: Primary Data

The table shows that out of 80 respondents, 20% of the respondents choose the reason price, 30% of the respondents choose the reason offers, 25% of the respondents choose the reason range of products, and 25% of the respondents choose the reason convenience. Most of the respondents choose the reason offers.

Table 6: Gender and Satisfaction Level of Shopping Experience

Gender	Level of Satisfaction				Total
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dis - Satisfied	Highly Dis - Satisfied	
Male	15 (28.5%)	14 (33.3%)	9 (17.14%)	4 (7.61%)	42
Female	5 (10.5%)	26 (54.7%)	4 (8.42%)	3 (6.31%)	38
Total	20	40	13	7	80

Ho = There is no significant association between Gender of the respondents and their satisfaction level of the shopping experience. Out of 80 respondents, 42% respondents are male of which, 15(28.5%) respondents have highly Satisfied, 14(33.3%) respondents are Satisfied, 9(17.14%) respondents are Dis-Satisfied, 4(7.61%) respondents are highly Dis-Satisfied. 38% respondents are female of which, 5(10.52%) respondents have highly Satisfied, 26(54.7%) have Satisfied, 4(8.42%) respondents are Dis - Satisfied while 3(6.31%) respondents have highly Dis-Satisfied. The percentage of respondents with high level of satisfaction is found high among male and the percentage of respondents with low level of satisfaction is found low among female. Since the calculated Chi – Square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there exist a significant association between Gender is level of satisfaction on Internet Advertisement.

Gender and Most Preferable Websites:

Ho = There is significant association between Gender of the respondents and their most preferable websites.

Table 7: Gender and Most Preferable Websites

Websites	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Flipkart.com	17 (34.8%)	22 (45.12%)	39
Olx.in	7 (56%)	3 (24%)	10
Quickr.com	8 (58.18%)	3 (21.8%)	11
Snapdeal.com	8 (35.5%)	10 (44.4%)	18
Others	2 (80%)	0 (0%)	2
Total	42	38	80

The table indicates, 39% respondents are Flipkart.com of which, 17 (34.8%) respondents are male and 22 (45.12%) have female. 10% respondents are Olx.in of which, 7 (56%) respondents have male and 3 (24%) respondents have female. 11% respondents are Quickr.com of which, 8 (58.18%) respondents have male while 3 (21.8%) respondents have female. 18% respondents are Snapdeal.com of which, 8 (35.5%) respondents have male while 10 (44.4%) of the respondents are female. 2% respondents are others of which, 2 (80%) respondents have male while 0 (0%) of the respondents are female. The percentage of respondents with high level of using websites is found high among Flipkart.com and the percentage of respondents with low level of using the websites is found low among others. Since the calculated Chi – Square value is lower than the table value at five per cent level, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there exist a significant association between gender and most preferable websites using the Internet Advertisement Viewers.

Suggestion:

Generally the purchase decision is Influence to Internet Advertisement Viewers.

- ✓ The respondents choosing the reason for offers, and the peoples opinion about the internet advertisement is easy to buy the products.
- ✓ Urban area respondents to know about the Internet Advertisement.
- ✓ The people daily accessing the internet.
- ✓ Internet advertisement is very attractive. So many viewers watching the internet advertisement.
- ✓ Electronic products are highly purchased to the internet advertisement.
- ✓ The male respondents are purchasing more products through the internet. But few female respondents are purchases the products.

Conclusion:

Internet advertising was effective in providing higher reach and creation of awareness. The study determined that there is a positive relationship between internet advertising and their purchase decision. Internet Advertisements are very reliable and providing right information about the product and service. Internet Advertising is very attractive and Time saving. Varieties of products are available in their websites. Easily buy the better quality of the products and low cost of the product price. It has no time limitations and can be viewed day and night through the globe. It also reduced the transaction cost. Internet Advertisement is very effective as it attracts lot of youngsters.

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